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1. Objectives of the Deliverable

The objective of this deliverable is to document the design, implementation, and validation of the technical workflow developed within WP7 for the digitisation, processing, and exploitation of medieval papal registers, with a specific focus on the creation of high-quality, machine-readable datasets supporting automatic regesta generation.

More specifically, the deliverable aims to:

- Define and standardise a complete digitisation and processing pipeline for historical papal sources, covering image preparation, binarisation, segmentation, transcription, and structured export, in order to ensure reproducibility, scalability, and interoperability of the workflow.
- Develop and evaluate customised HTR and layout segmentation models tailored to the complex typographic and editorial structure of 19th- and 20th-century critical editions of papal registers, overcoming the limitations of pre-existing generic models.
- Produce and document structured datasets (REVERINO and REVERINO II) consisting of aligned text–regestum pairs in medieval Latin, suitable for training, evaluating, and benchmarking automatic summarisation and regesta generation systems.
- Ensure data quality, traceability, and reusability through systematic metadata collection, controlled post-processing procedures, and adherence to FAIR principles, enabling long-term reuse of the datasets in research, teaching, and infrastructure contexts.
- Test the applicability of the produced datasets in downstream NLP and LLM-based tasks, through a first controlled experiment in automatic regesta generation, assessing both quantitative performance and qualitative adequacy of generated outputs.
- Lay the technical and methodological foundations for future extensions of the corpus, including the integration of additional papal registers from the Bibliothèque des Écoles françaises d'Athènes and the refinement of models capable of handling increasingly heterogeneous documentary layouts.

2. HTR Processing of Documents

2.1 Setting up the digitisation process

In the initial phase of the REVER project, focused on digitising the corpus, technical specifications were defined for PDF-to-JPG export. It was decided that uploading individual JPG files to eScriptorium was preferable to using multi page PDFs, in order to avoid upload errors and ensure a more flexible structure. The images were generated using Foxit PDF Editor, with an optimal resolution of 236.22 pixels/cm and RGB colour space.

2.1.1 Choice of image format and PDF conversion

The choice of image format for uploading to eScriptorium was guided by criteria of compatibility, visual quality, and the platform's operational stability. During the preliminary phase, it became clear that processing high-resolution, large-size PDF files led to significant slowdowns and, in several cases, system crashes during upload or segmentation. To address these issues, the digitised volumes in PDF format were converted into raster images, preferably in JPEG format, selecting an intermediate resolution that offered a good balance between legibility and file size. This resolution ensured adequate quality of the written content, while avoiding distortions or compression artefacts.

The output was tested with bulk uploads to eScriptorium to verify full compatibility and to ensure a smooth, stable, and efficient workflow within the annotation and segmentation environment.

2.1.2 Export tests from Foxit and selection of optimal resolution

The Foxit software was used for the conversion of PDF files into raster images. Provided among the project resources, Foxit served as the standard tool for document management and export. Several export tests were conducted using this tool to assess the impact of resolution settings on the balance between visual quality and file size. In particular, different resolution levels were tested, with the aim of ensuring maximum text legibility without compromising the stability and upload performance of the eScriptorium platform.

The selected resolution was 236.22 pixels/cm, equivalent to approximately 600 dpi. This configuration guaranteed high sharpness and character clarity, while keeping the file size within the acceptable limits for uploading.

Tests were also performed using higher resolutions, but they did not yield any significant improvements in OCR/HTR quality, while noticeably increasing file size beyond practical thresholds. For this reason, the value of 236.22 pixels/cm was adopted as the operational standard for converting selected booklets within the project workflow.

These settings were chosen to ensure maximum visual quality during PDF-to-JPEG conversion, while keeping the file sizes manageable for subsequent processing in eScriptorium.

Image export specifications from PDF (Foxit):

Output mode:

single-page export (one JPEG per each page of the PDF).

Image file format:

Greyscale: JPEG with maximum quality.

Colour: JPEG with maximum quality.

Compression format:

Baseline (optimised).

Conversion:

Colour space: RGB.

Resolution: 236.22 pixels/cm (equivalent to approximately 600 dpi).

Figure1 – Image export window in JPEG format from Foxit, with resolution set to 236.22 pixels/cm

Pixels per cm	DPI
28,35 pixels/cm	72 dpi
37,80 pixels/cm	96 dpi
59,06 pixels/cm	150 dpi
118,11 pixels/cm	300 dpi
236,22 pixels/cm	600 dpi
472,44 pixels/cm	1200 dpi
944,88 pixels/cm	2400 dpi

Table 1 – Correspondence between resolution expressed in pixels per centimeter (pixel/cm) and dots per inch (DPI). The values shown correspond to the standard resolution options available in Foxit software for exporting images from PDF files.

2.1.3 Organisation of folders and logical structure in eScriptorium

To ensure an orderly, traceable, and scalable workflow, a hierarchical structure was established for organizing the text images within eScriptorium. Document groups were subdivided based on the following criteria: pope, volume, and page. After being exported and renamed according to a consistent naming convention, the raster images were uploaded to eScriptorium in separate collections, each corresponding to a single volume (or a part thereof, in the case of particularly large fascicles). The work sessions in eScriptorium were structured to mirror this organization precisely, allowing for accurate mapping between image, text segment, and associated metadata.

The file naming system was designed to facilitate automatic alignment between the images and output data, incorporating unique identifiers for the pontificate, register number, and page position. This approach not only supported efficient internal navigation but also streamlined the export and reprocessing of segmented and transcribed data in ALTO, XML, or JSON formats. Volumes were tagged according to whether they contained the main *text* of the papal registers or their *index*, and were also marked as *model* when appropriate.

The folder structure was designed to support the potential reuse and re-alignment of data in environments external to eScriptorium (such as archival platforms or automatic regesta generation systems), making the system modular and interoperable with other historical digitisation tools.

2.1.4 Criteria for excluding index volumes

In selecting the corpus to be segmented and transcribed in eScriptorium, volumes consisting solely of indexes were excluded – namely, the dossiers containing only lists of names, rubrics, cross-references, or editorial summaries.

This decision was based on two main considerations. First, such volumes lack textual content with syntactic or diplomatic structures suitable for automatic regesta generation. Second, their content is unsuitable for training or evaluating Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) or Natural Language Processing (NLP) models, due to its fragmentary and repetitive content, which is not suited to regesta extraction.

Excluding index volumes allowed for a more efficient allocation of resources, focusing efforts on material directly relevant to the development and evaluation of recognition and summarisation models. In the future, these volumes may be processed separately for documentary or advanced indexing purposes, but they are not included in the core corpus intended for automatic regesta generation.

2.1.5 Binarization of images

Before initiating segmentation and transcription operations in eScriptorium, a preliminary binarization phase was deemed appropriate. This procedure involves converting greyscale images into binary images, in which each pixel takes on a value of either black or white only.

The aim of binarisation is twofold: on the one hand, to enhance the contrast between text and background, thereby facilitating the automatic identification of lines and textual areas; on the other, to reduce “visual noise” caused by stained backgrounds, irregular borders, stamps, or marginal marks, which could interfere with segmentation and text recognition. Binarization was applied only when the visual quality of the images required it, particularly in cases where contrast was insufficient or the presence of graphic artefacts risked compromising the quality of automatic segmentation.

This operation contributed to visually standardising the images and improving the accuracy of the automatic annotation process, especially in handwritten or typewritten sections that were difficult to read.

2.2 Training layout models

Given the complexity of the typographic layout of the papal registers, it was necessary to develop a specific segmentation model entitled «Alessandro IV Semplificato – 24 novembre 2024 – Sabbatini». This model was derived from the base model

«2col_humanum_04_289imgs_w_margs_99.mlmodel», and was adapted through training on 30, then 60, and finally 100 pages, selected according to the complexity of the page layout.

2.2.1 Limitations of pre-existing layout models

During the automatic segmentation of historical documents in the eScriptorium platform, the use of predefined layout models revealed a number of critical issues, particularly when applied to editions of medieval documents with non-standard graphic structures. The pre-existing models, developed on specific corpora, are not easily generalisable when applied to documents with differing characteristics, such as variations in text arrangement, presence of marginal notes, column indicators, headers and footers, notes embedded within the main column rather than in footnotes, or irregular column distribution. These shortcomings became especially apparent in cases involving complex layouts with multi-column text, marginal annotations, or interfering graphic elements. As a result, the application of pre-existing models often required significant manual intervention to correct missegmented text areas, increasing the time and resources needed to complete the transcription process.

Moreover, the structure of these models is tightly bound to the original training data, which does not include representative examples of the specific features found in editions of papal registers. This dependency makes it difficult to adapt the models to new documentary domains without substantial retraining.

Overall, the effectiveness of the pre-existing models proved insufficient to ensure a smooth, accurate, and scalable workflow. This clearly highlighted the need to design and train custom layout models capable of handling the structural complexity of the documents under study, and of integrating fully into the automatic segmentation and transcription process.

2.2.2 Development of the «Alessandro IV Semplificato» model

In light of the limitations observed in pre-existing layout models, a customised segmentation model was developed under the name «Alessandro IV Semplificato», designed specifically for processing the booklets of the papal register corresponding to the pontificate of Alexander IV.

The model was built on the basis of a manual segmentation campaign carried out on a representative subset of images from the volume *Les Registres d'Alexandre IV (1254/61)*, edited by C. Bourel, De La Roncière, J. De Loye, and A. Coulon (series of the École Française d'Athènes), Paris, 1902. The images were selected according to their layout features, with the aim of training the model to handle the specific structural challenges posed by the text.

Compared to a more detailed initial version, it became necessary to simplify the model due to a significant technical constraint: eScriptorium is currently unable to reliably distinguish both footers and in-text notes when the latter are embedded within the columns rather than placed at the bottom of the page. This overlap made it difficult to automatically differentiate between content types, thus reducing the effectiveness of segmentation.

The goal was to create a model that is both robust and streamlined, capable of accurately identifying the main text regions, while excluding irrelevant parts during text export and the subsequent automatic generation of regesta.

The simplification of the model was guided by the systematic removal of headers, footers, column and page numbers, and any notes unrelated to the main text, with the aim of isolating only diplomatically relevant content. This focus on a «clean» and recurring layout accelerated the training process and improved its efficiency, reducing the need for later manual corrections.

The model was subsequently tested on adjacent volumes from the same chronological period, showing a good degree of transferability to documents with a similar structure. «Alessandro IV Semplificato» thus constitutes a first prototype of a segmentation model tailored to the corpus of papal registers, intended to be extended and refined in future, more complex and generalisable models.

2.2.3 Definition of ontology and region management

During the segmentation phase, it was necessary to define an ontology aimed at distinguishing and classifying the various textual regions, in order to facilitate the alignment between image, transcription, and the logical structure of the regesta. This enables to identify the different components of the document layout, with the objective of isolating the text segments relevant for transcription and automatic processing.

The adopted ontology was deliberately kept minimal in order to ensure maximum stability and compatibility with subsequent export and processing phases. The following region types were activated and managed, as specified in the ontology tab in eScriptorium:

Column left, Column right:	for the main columns
Footer, Header:	for the header and footer
Note left, Note right:	for the right and left notes
Number left, Number right:	for the column numbers
Page:	for the page numbers
Title	for the title of the volume or section

Table 2: Tagging system used to distinguish the different textual regions in the digitized volumes

As for the line types associated with the corresponding regions, the following were activated: Column left, Column right, Footer, Header, Note left, Note right, Number left, Number right, Page, and Title.

Figure 2 – “Ontology” section in eScriptorium, displaying the list of activated region and line types.

Figure 3 Colour scheme of segmentation regions in eScriptorium.

As can be seen in Figure 3, each colour represents a type of region activated in the project’s ontology. Yellow and purple areas indicate the column numbers (*Number left, Number right*); pink

and orange areas indicate the left (*Column left*) and right (*Column right*) columns respectively; red identifies the header (*Header*), blue marks the footer (*Footer*). Light blue and green areas indicate the notes (*Note left, Note right*).

In the first image of Figure 4, the following elements are clearly distinguishable:

- *Header region* (red): corresponds to the current header at the top.
- *Footer region* (blue): corresponds to the footer at the bottom.
- *Number left* and *Number right* regions (yellow and purple): highlight the column numbers.
- *Column left region* (pink): represents the left-hand text column.
- *Column right region* (orange): represents the right-hand column.
- *Note right* and *Note left* regions (light blue and green): highlight the notes inserted in the respective columns.

Figure 4 The two images show two pages segmented in eScriptorium. Each area of the page is highlighted in a different color, corresponding to a region type defined in the project's ontology.

Region management was carried out with particular attention to consistency across volumes and to the repeatability of annotation, in order to enable the training and evaluation of more general segmentation models in subsequent phases. However, after observing that eScriptorium tends to identify notes imprecisely when they are embedded within the text columns rather than in the footer, it was decided to deactivate the Note left and Note right categories, as well as the recognition of their corresponding lines.

The ambiguity in recognising in-column notes posed the risk that entire sections of relevant text might be excluded during export, having been mistakenly classified as notes. To prevent the

loss of valuable content, a more controllable solution was adopted: only the footer regions would be detected, as they can be easily excluded during export. Notes were instead removed in bulk during the post-processing phase. This led to the training of a second simplified model, which proved effective for segmenting the volumes of the Reverse Regesta corpus.

This rationalisation of the ontology made it possible to improve segmentation accuracy, reduce the need for manual corrections, and ensure greater consistency during export, particularly in structured formats (ALTO XML, JSON) used for automatic regesta generation.

The goal of ontological simplification was to facilitate the training of robust and consistent models, minimising confusion between similar categories. The resulting system enables effective region traceability, simplifies manual intervention in the event of errors, and lays the groundwork for future interoperability with semantic processing tools and automatic regesta generation. Reducing the number of categories also helped limit classification errors and simplified manual correction in cases of structural or graphical ambiguity.

2.2.4 Comparison with the baseline model

The “Alessandro IV Semplificato” model was developed from the pre-existing model “2col_humanum_04_28gimgs_w_margs_99”. This is a model trained for the segmentation of humanistic texts with a complex but regular editorial structure. However, applying this model to the volume *Les Registres d’Alexandre IV (1254–1261)*, edited by C. Bourel, De La Roncière, J. De Loye, and A. Coulon (Paris, 1902), revealed significant limitations for this particular case: in particular, the frequent presence of notes placed at the bottom of the columns, instead of in the footer, compromised the system’s ability to correctly distinguish between the main text and ancillary content. This ambiguity created a real risk that entire sections of relevant text might be mistakenly excluded during export, due to the imprecise classification of regions containing notes. To address this issue, the “Alessandro IV Semplificato” model retained the general structure of the baseline model, but introduced significant changes in the management of the layout. This revision improved the stability and consistency of the model, reducing the need for manual corrections and making the entire workflow— from segmentation to export in structured format— more reliable. The resulting model proved well-suited to the specific structure of the 19th-century edition of the registers of Alexander IV, offering an effective balance between precision, simplicity, and operational control.

2.3 Choosing the transcription model for Latin

During the experimentation phase, a series of tests were conducted on various HTR (Handwritten Text Recognition) models available in eScriptorium, with the aim of assessing their effectiveness in recognising 19th- and 20th-century printed editions of papal texts in medieval ecclesiastical Latin. These editions often feature dense and irregular typography, column layouts,

frequent use of Latin abbreviations, and complex historical typefaces, such as the long s (ſ) and ligatures like “fe”, “ct”, “ae”, and “oe”, which are frequently misinterpreted by models that have not been specifically trained on them.

Although these writing styles are perfectly correct from a historical usage perspective, they compromise the output quality of automatic transcription. For this reason, an HTR system was chosen instead of a traditional OCR: unlike OCR, which relies on the recognition of standardised printed characters and works better on modern texts, HTR allows the training of models on historical editions, taking into account graphic variations, ligatures, archaic character shapes, and irregular punctuation. This approach has proven more suitable for handling the typographic complexity of papal sources, offering greater accuracy in rendering the original text.

2.3.1 Assessment of pre-existing OCR files

The text files available in major digital repositories - such as Internet Archive, Google Books, or DMGH - are often based on OCR carried out years ago using technologies that are now outdated. While these files can be useful for preliminary consultation, they often exhibit highly variable recognition quality, with errors that compromise the automatic analysis or scientific reuse of the texts for research on automatic regesta generation.

The gradual obsolescence of these OCR files—especially in terms of transcription accuracy—is linked to the rapid evolution of image-to-text technologies: in recent years, recognition systems have significantly improved, both in terms of accuracy and in their ability to handle complex layouts, specific scripts, and historical languages. For this reason, it was considered necessary to undertake new scanning of the volumes, combined with a text recognition performed with updated softwares, to ensure the reliability, readability, and interoperability of the data produced.

2.3.2 Transcription models for Medieval Latin

The HTR models made available through platforms such as eScriptorium are the result of careful palaeographic adaptation. They have been trained on Latin corpora while taking into account the graphic specificities of the sources and morphological variants, and are designed to recognise not only handwritten characters, but also historical conventions of Latin script such as abbreviations and ligatures.

In the case of REVER, the application did not involve handwritten texts, but 19th- and 20th-century printed editions of papal texts in ecclesiastical Latin, characterised by a typeface that often reproduces medieval textual forms and structures. The presence of elements such as the long s, ligatures (such as fe, æ, ct), Latin abbreviations, and an irregular use of punctuation made it necessary to carefully assess the available models.

The goal was not merely to identify the most accurate model, but the one most functional for the type of transcription we were dealing with—a transcription based on modern editions that nevertheless preserve some of the formal complexities of medieval documentary Latin. The

evaluation considered overall output quality, stability in multi-column layouts, and the model's ability to coherently reproduce the distinctive features of historical typography.

2.3.3 Evaluation of available HTR models

Among the models tested were «gallicorpora_best»¹, optimised for French manuscripts, and «catmus-print-fondue-large»², designed for historical printed texts. The latter proved to be more suitable for the context: it showed a greater ability to correctly recognise composite characters and ligatures typical of 19th-century publishing, as well as greater consistency in handling punctuation and spacing within columns.

Based on these evaluations, «catmus-print-fondue-large» was selected as the main operational model. It was tested on the transcription of documents related to Pope Alexander IV, taken from the volume *Les Registres d'Alexandre IV (1254–1261)*. The identification of «catmus-print-fondue-large» followed the in-house development of the segmentation model «Alessandro IV Semplificato», enabling a progressively refined transcription and serving as the foundation for future adaptation to other papal volumes in the same series.

2.3.4 Transcription workflow setup

At this stage, the operational process through which segmented images are converted into machine-readable text was defined and organised. The transcription workflow includes the configuration of recognition tools, optional output normalisation, and quality control of the results. The objective is to ensure a coherent, efficient, and reproducible pipeline capable of producing accurate transcriptions aligned with the project standards.

The stages of the workflow are:

- A. Importing the images in JPG format
- B. Organising the volumes within the project workspace
- C. Binarising the images to optimise contrast and facilitate subsequent phases
- D. Segmenting the pages using the «Alessandro IV Semplificato» model, developed to identify different textual regions
- E. Automatic transcription using the HTR model «catmus-print-fondue-large», specifically trained on medieval Latin texts
- F. Exporting the results in ALTO format (for structure and text positioning) and TXT format (for linear content extraction)

2.3.5 Large-scale application of models in eScriptorium

Following the development, testing, and validation phases of the segmentation and transcription models, large-scale application was launched within the eScriptorium platform. This

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/7410529>

² <https://zenodo.org/records/10592716>

phase involved the mass processing of entire digitised volumes, using the system's batch functionalities to handle hundreds of images in an automated workflow.

The eScriptorium infrastructure, installed on a dedicated CNR server, enabled the simultaneous management of multiple projects and the optimisation of processing times. The models were applied directly to the segmented images, following the predefined workflows (binarisation, segmentation, transcription, export), ensuring consistency in processing and traceability of operations.

The large-scale application allowed for testing the robustness and scalability of the system, as well as identifying potential issues linked to data heterogeneity (different layouts, image quality, presence of marginal annotations). During this phase, it was also possible to establish monitoring criteria for transcription accuracy and to identify any need to adapt the models to specific graphic or chronological contexts.

2.4 Application of the models to the REVER corpora

The models developed were applied at scale to the REVER corpora, using images processed according to the project's standard pipeline:

upload JPG → binarization → segmentation → automatic transcription.

Only the main textual regions were retained for processing, corresponding to *Column left* and *Column right*. All other regions — *Header*, *Footer*, *Note left*, *Note right*, *Number left*, *Number right*, *Page*, *Title* — were excluded in order to reduce paratextual noise and obtain a homogeneous output suitable for the alignment and automatic summarisation phase.

2.4.1 Application of the models to available corpora

The REVERINO corpus represents the primary documentary foundation for all summarisation work developed within the project. It consists of a structured dataset of 4,533 text–regestum pairs, built from medieval papal documents in Latin, each matched with its corresponding summarised regestum.

The corpus was built using two collections: *Epistolae saeculi XIII e regestis pontificum Romanorum selectae* (Epp. saec. XIII) in the *Monumenta Germaniae Historica* (MGH) and the series published by the École Française d'Athènes.

The following MGH collections were used:

- *Ex Honori III registro*, in *Epistolae saeculi XIII e regestis pontificum Romanorum selectae*, vol 1, ed. K. Rodenberg, Berolini, 1883;
- *Ex Innocenti IV registro*, *Epistolae saeculi XIII e regestis pontificum Romanorum selectae*, vol. 2, ed. K. Rodenberg, Munchen, 1982;
- *Ex Clementis IV registro*, *Epistolae saeculi XIII e regestis pontificum Romanorum selectae*, vol. 3, ed. K. Rodenberg, Munchen, 1982;

For the series published by the École Française d'Athènes, the following were used:

- *Les Registres de Grégoire IX (1227/41)* ed. L. Auvray, 1 tomo, Paris, 1896;
- *Les Registres de Grégoire IX (1227/41)* ed. L. Auvray, 2 tomo, Paris, 1902;
- *Les Registres de Grégoire IX (1227/41)* ed. L. Auvray, 3 tomo, Paris, 1908;
- *Les Registres de Grégoire IX (1227/41)* ed. L. Auvray, 4 tomo, Paris, 1955;
- *Les Registres d'Innocent IV (1243/54)*, ed. E. Berger, 1 tomo, Paris, 1884;
- *Les Registres d'Innocent IV (1243/54)*, ed. E. Berger, 2 tomo, Paris, 1887;
- *Les Registres d'Innocent IV (1243/54)*, ed. E. Berger, 3 tomo, Paris, 1897;
- *Les Registres d'Innocent IV (1243/54)*, ed. E. Berger, 4 tomo, Paris, 1897;

Building on the results obtained with REVERINO, the models were subsequently applied to the REVERINO II corpus, which includes a broader selection of papal registers. The application to REVERINO II made it possible to test the system's ability to adapt to non-normalised texts, characterised by higher informational density and lower syntactic regularity.

The REVERINO II corpus includes the following volumes from the series published by the École Française d'Athènes:

- *Les Registres d'Alexandre IV (1254/61)*, 1 tomo, ed. C. Bourel, de la Roncière, J. De loye, et a. Coulon, Paris, 1902;
- *Les Registres d'Alexandre IV (1254/61)*, 2 tomo, ed. C. Bourel, de la Roncière, J. De loye, et a. Coulon, Paris, 1917;
- *Les Registres d'Alexandre IV (1254/61)*, 3 tomo, ed. C. Bourel, de la Roncière, J. De loye, et a. Coulon, Paris, 1953;
- *Les Registres d'Alexandre IV (1254/61)*, 4 tomo, ed. C. Bourel, de la Roncière, J. De loye, et a. Coulon, Paris, 1959;
- *Les Registres d'Urbain IV (1261/64)*, 1 tomo, ed. M. J. Guiraud, Paris, 1901
- *Les Registres d'Urbain IV (1261/64)*, 2 tomo, ed. M. J. Guiraud, Paris, 1901
- *Les Registres d'Urbain IV (1261/64)*, 3 tomo, ed. M. J. Guiraud, Paris, 1904
- *Les Registres d'Urbain IV (1261/64)*, 4 tomo, ed. M. J. Guiraud, Paris, 1929

2.4.2 Exporting machine-readable texts

For the construction of the dataset, the segmented and transcribed files were exported in two formats:

- ALTO (XML): including structural information and textual coordinates.
- Text (TXT): for the generation of text/regestum pairs.

The export was carried out selectively, including only certain elements from the project ontology deemed relevant to the automatic summarisation phase. The initial attempt to automatically distinguish between note regions (embedded within columns) and footers led to segmentation errors, with the unintended consequence of excluding relevant portions from the main body of text.

To reduce noise and ensure a coherent dataset, it was decided to exclude footers and retain notes, since the latter appeared less frequently and were harder to detect as distinct regions. For this reason, a subsequent IT fine-tuning phase was required, aimed at refining the export and removing residual paratextual elements in order to preserve the integrity of the significant text blocks. This refinement work is still ongoing, in collaboration with the CNR technical support team.

Figure 5 shows the ALTO export configuration, with the selection of the main textual regions (*Column left* and *Column right*) and the exclusion of paratextual elements (*Footer*, *Header*, *Title*, etc.), in order to generate an output optimised for the automatic summarisation phase.

1 image(s) selected. ?

kraken:catmus-print-fondue-large

ALTO

Include images
Will significantly increase the time to produce and download the export.

Region types

Title Column left Column right Footer

Header Page (Undefined region type)

(Orphan lines)

Close Export

Figure 5 – Export window from eScriptorium.

2.4.3 Post-processing (cleaning of the REVERINO dataset)

The output from eScriptorium consists of a series of text lines associated with spatial information indicating their position on the page. To convert these data into structured documents containing extended text, regestum, and critical apparatus, a set of heuristics was applied to sequentially analyse the lines and identify document boundaries—specifically, by detecting the lines that mark the end of a text based on their distance from the following line.

This approach makes it possible to isolate text blocks, each containing a coherent unit composed of extended text, regestum, and apparatus. The second step involves separating these three components in order to create a new record for each document, which is useful for automatic text–regestum alignment and for training automatic regesta generation models.

To this end, a second set of heuristics is applied to identify the boundaries between the three sections. In particular, spatial distance on the page is used to distinguish the extended text

from the regestum, since it is standard practice in the analysed manuscripts to leave a blank space or a separating paragraph between these two parts. To separate the regestum from the critical apparatus, string-based heuristics are adopted. These rely on the recognition of recurring typographic and syntactic elements – such as parentheses, quotation marks, asterisks, or editorial symbols – which reliably indicate the beginning of the apparatus in relation to the main body of the regestum.

2.4.4 Post-processing (cleaning of the REVERINO II dataset)

To transform the output from eScriptorium into the same format used for Reverino and make it usable for training generative models for automatic regesta generation, we used a hybrid approach that leverages a complementary use of heuristics and generative AI. Specifically, we applied high-level heuristics to separate the set of transcribed text lines from eScriptorium into regesta blocks, removing most of the spatial metadata that indicate the position of the text on the page. We then used GPT-4o to aggregate the lines into extended texts, regesta, and apparatus sections.

To achieve this, we developed a custom prompt and subsequently discarded texts returned by ChatGPT that showed defects. Although this approach is less deterministic than the one used for Reverino, it allows us to process large volumes of data without having to develop ad hoc heuristics for each new collection of regesta and each new manuscript, which may present different imperfections depending on the training performed in eScriptorium.

2.5 Technical rationale

The selection of the workflow and of the technical tools adopted in this deliverable was guided by a combination of methodological, operational, and sustainability criteria, closely aligned with the specific characteristics of the documentary corpus and the objectives of WP7. First, priority was given to solutions capable of handling the structural and typographic complexity of 19th- and 20th-century critical editions of medieval papal registers, which feature dense layouts, multi-column pagination, embedded notes, and non-standard typographic conventions. This requirement motivated the choice of a workflow centred on image-based processing and Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR), rather than relying on pre-existing OCR outputs, which proved inadequate in terms of accuracy and reliability for scientific reuse.

Second, the workflow was designed to ensure modularity, reproducibility, and scalability, allowing individual processing stages – as image preparation, binarisation, segmentation, transcription, export, and post-processing - to be independently controlled, evaluated, and refined. The adoption of eScriptorium as the core processing environment was driven by its support for custom model training, its compatibility with structured export formats (ALTO XML, TXT, JSON), and its ability

to integrate segmentation, transcription, and large-scale batch processing within a single, traceable framework.

Tool selection was further informed by interoperability and long-term reuse considerations. Preference was given to widely adopted, research-oriented platforms and open or well-documented standards, in order to facilitate data exchange, integration with downstream NLP and LLM-based pipelines, and compliance with FAIR data principles. The choice of specific segmentation and transcription models was empirically validated through iterative testing on representative subsets of the corpus, privileging solutions that offered the best balance between recognition accuracy, robustness across heterogeneous layouts, and controllability of errors during export and post-processing.

Finally, the overall workflow reflects a pragmatic balance between automation and scholarly control. While maximising automation was essential for processing large volumes of material, particular attention was paid to preserving the possibility of manual intervention, quality checks, and corrective post-processing.

3. Dataset

3.1 First data block – REVERINO

The REVERINO dataset represents the first data block processed within the project. It includes the registers of Gregory IX, selected from two key critical editions: *Epistolae saeculi XIII e regestis pontificum Romanorum selectae*, published in the *Monumenta Germaniae Historica* (MGH), and *Les Registres de Grégoire IX*, edited by Lucien Auvray (BEF). The dataset contains over 4,500 text/registum pairs and was built through a complete pipeline that included digitisation, binarisation, segmentation, and automatic transcription. A sample-based manual review was carried out in parallel, comparing the original text with the transcribed version, in order to identify lexical, symbolic, and structural issues.

3.2 Second data block – REVERINO II

The second dataset, named REVERINO II, represents an evolution of the corpus, both in terms of scale and documentary complexity. It includes the editions *Les Registres d’Alexandre IV* (BEF) and *Les Registres d’Urban IV* (BEF). Compared to REVERINO, the REVERINO II dataset introduces greater variability in layouts—ranging from single-column pagination to double-column formats with independent numbering—as well as in scan quality and the structure of textual regions. The processing pipeline (upload, binarisation, segmentation, transcription) remained consistent, but enhanced manual checks and post-processing activities were required, particularly for cleaning footnotes and harmonising margins. Here too, the textual content was exported using selective criteria, including only the textual regions relevant for the subsequent automatic summarisation phase.

3.3 Dataset expansion – Bibliothèque des Écoles Française d’Athènes

Following the development of the REVERINO and REVERINO II datasets, a systematic effort was launched to expand the corpus, based on the full series of papal registers published by the *École Française d’Athènes et de Rome* (BEF), currently undergoing progressive acquisition and organisation. This choice is motivated by the scientific value of the collection and by the fact that it contains both regesta and full documents presented in sequence—a feature that makes it particularly suitable for automatic processing and integration into the workflow already tested on REVERINO and REVER.

The BEF collection, launched in Paris in 1884, represents one of the most important editorial undertakings dedicated to papal documentation. Each volume is based on direct transcription of

the original manuscripts preserved in the Vatican Archives and presents a rich internal structure. The volumes are organised by pontificate and are edited by leading scholars such as Elie Berger, Lucien Auvray, Jean Guiraud, and Ernest Langlois, characterised by high critical rigour and editorial clarity.

The collection spans the 13th and 14th centuries and encompasses a large succession of pontificates and registers. It represents a vast and multi-layered documentary heritage, serving as a strategic resource for expanding the REVER corpus both chronologically and in terms of the structural diversity of textual data. This collection provides critical editions of papal registers based on original manuscripts preserved in the Vatican Archives, offering rich and well-structured documentation valuable for both automatic processing with digital tools and historical analysis. The variety and heterogeneity of the editions within this collection present new challenges regarding bibliographic normalization and the adaptation of the automatic processing pipeline. Simultaneously, they create extensive opportunities for in-depth investigation and experimentation, particularly in training more robust models capable of managing diverse layouts, formats, and editorial conventions.

3.4 Collections excluded from the REVER processing campaign

During the construction of the REVER corpus, several historical editorial collections of papal registers and regesta were analysed. However, some of these were not included in the automatic processing campaign due to issues such as poor digitisation quality, structural incompatibility with automatic segmentation criteria, lack of complete editions, or the secondary or retrospective nature of the sources.

Among the excluded collections are:

- O.S.B. – *Regesta Clementis PP. V* (1305–1314)
Edition curated by the Benedictine monks (O.S.B.), lacking structured indices and difficult to segment.
- KEHR – *Regesta Pontificum Romanorum*
Includes the *Germania Pontificia*, *Italia Pontificia*, *Gallia Pontificia*, and *Dalmatia-Croatia Pontificia* series. Although widely used in historiography, its descriptive structure and editorial organisation are not compatible with the automatic extraction of text/regestum pairs.
- PRESUTTI – *Regesta Honorii III*
Incomplete edition with irregular layout and textual markup.

- EUBEL – *Register des Gegenpapstes Nikolaus V (1328–1330)*
A text of historical value, but lacking consistent structure.
- OTTENTHAL – *Bullenregister Martin V*
Edition published within a miscellaneous volume, difficult to isolate.
- JAFFÉ – *Regesta Pontificum Romanorum usque ad annum 1198*
Although foundational in the history of regesta compilation, this collection is unsuitable for training extraction models on structured textual sources.

These collections nonetheless remain scientifically relevant and may, at a later stage, serve as material for manual comparison or be the subject of alternative processing, in non-automated contexts or through tools for advanced lexical normalisation.

3.5 Repository and continuous updates

The datasets produced during the project have been progressively structured, documented, and made available in open access, in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and best practices in research data management. Each dataset corresponds to a specific phase in the development of the automatic regesta generation system and reflects increasing complexity and diversity in the sources used.

The first published corpus is REVERINO, the result of the initial activities of annotation, segmentation, transcription, and alignment between full texts and regesta. REVERINO is based on selected 19th-century editions of papal registers and features a highly normalised structure suitable for training models for automatic summarisation. It includes transcribed and segmented texts, consistently annotated with metadata, and supplemented by supporting documentation.

The output relating to REVERINO has been exported in ALTO (XML) format, for preserving spatial and structural information, and TXT format, for generating text–regestum pairs. The export included only a selection of categories from the project ontology, based on their relevance to the summarisation process. During this phase, heuristics were adopted to separate documents and textual layers (full text, regestum, apparatus), followed by further IT fine-tuning to remove paratextual elements and restore the integrity of the meaningful textual blocks.

All processed files (XML, TXT) have been progressively collected in a public repository. The repository is maintained according to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Each update is subject to controlled versioning and traceability. The system is designed to gradually include the datasets currently under development.

The REVERINO dataset has been published on Zenodo, within a dedicated repository, available at the following address: <https://zenodo.org/records/14971613> . The repository is

accompanied by a detailed descriptive sheet, technical documentation, and an open licence allowing for scientific and educational use.

Subsequently, the same structuring process was extended to the REVER corpus, characterised by greater variety and complexity. REVER includes a broader selection of papal registers, organised by pontiff, year of pontificate, and volume, and provides a more realistic basis for evaluating model performance in less standardised scenarios. Efforts are currently focused on the development and refinement of an extended dataset, integrating supplementary sources from the digitized holdings of the École française d'Athènes. This tertiary dataset is intended to rigorously evaluate the system's robustness across a heterogeneous corpus, encompassing both manuscript and printed documents. Upon completion of post-processing and quality validation, the dataset will be deposited and disseminated via Zenodo to ensure accessibility for further research and development.

3.6 Release in the ITSERR marketplace

The first publicly shared package within the REVER project is the REVERINO dataset. This dataset was selected for initial release as it had already undergone verification, cleaning, segmentation, and alignment, thereby meeting the quality and traceability requirements for open-access publication. The resource will be made available through the ITSERR Marketplace, with the aim of supporting research activities, methodological experimentation, and advanced training in the fields of Digital Humanities, automatic regesta generation, and text processing assisted by language models. The information included in the Zenodo release is as follows.

REVERINO contains 4,533 text/regestum pairs in Medieval Latin, drawn from two key collections:

- *Epistolae saeculi XIII e regestis pontificum Romanorum selectae* (MGH);
- *Les Registres de Grégoire IX* (BEF).

The dataset was built through a pipeline structured in four phases:

1. Manual annotation of the images using eScriptorium;
2. Training of segmentation models tailored to the specific structure of the manuscripts;
3. Automatic extraction of text lines;
4. Post-processing to separate extended text, regestum, and apparatus, using heuristics based on content and position.

The shared package includes:

- *JSON files containing the complete data structure (extended text, regestum, apparatus, header, identifier number);*
- *Active links to the PDFs of the original sources;*
- *A README file with technical documentation of the adopted pipeline;*
- *Data exported in ALTO (XML) and TXT formats, intended for reuse in research, training, and educational contexts.*

The release follows the CC BY 4.0 licence, allowing free reuse of the data provided that scientific credit is given to the curators: Giovanni Puccetti, Laura Righi, Ilaria Sabbatini, and Andrea Esuli. The dataset serves as a benchmark for evaluating LLMs in the automatic summarisation of historical texts in Latin.

4. Metadata collection and management

4.1 Structure and criteria of the metadata table

For each volume included in the REVERINO, REVERINO II, and BEF expansion datasets, a metadata table was created following a consistent structure. Each entry includes the name of the pope, the reference year, the volume or fascicle, the digitisation status (which may be indicated as not scanned, PDF, JPEG, HTR, or in refinement), and, when available, a direct link to the online PDF. This organisation makes it possible to effectively monitor the progress of the work, standardise activity tracking, and ensure alignment between editorial identification and the operational pipeline, from the image stage through to the export of machine-readable text.

4.2 Metadata organisation: Reverino, Reverino II, BEF expansion

The Excel file collecting the metadata for the datasets defined by the project is divided into three separate sheets: REVERINO, REVERINO II, and BEF Expansion. The REVERINO sheet forms the initial core and includes the three volumes of *Epistolae saeculi XIII et regestis pontificum Romanorum selectae* (MGH) and the three volumes of *Les Registres de Grégoire IX* (BEF).

The REVERINO II sheet represents the expanded corpus, covering the three volumes of *Les Registres d'Alexandre IV* (BEF) and the three volumes of *Les Registres d'Urbain IV* (BEF). The BEF Expansion sheet documents the further development phase, based on volumes published by the École Française d'Athènes.

Each section includes indicators relating to the processing status, using standardised labels such as "SCANNED", "OCR", "HTR", or "COMPLETED". It also contains technical notes, chronologies, identifying codes, and direct links to the reference PDF files, where available in the public domain. The overall structure is designed to ensure activity traceability and to support efficient consultation by various user groups, including historians, IT specialists, and librarians.

Metadata curation constitutes a foundational prerequisite for ensuring the coherence, traceability, and overall efficiency of the automatic processing pipeline. It enables precise documentation of source materials, facilitates the monitoring of technical workflows, and supports seamless interoperability across pipeline components—including HTR, NLP, and LLM modules. Furthermore, the availability of accurate and structured metadata guarantees the scientific citability of the datasets, supports advanced quality assurance procedures, promotes reusability in external research environments, and ensures alignment with the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) for responsible data management.

- Scan status (e.g. completed, to do, partial)
- HTR processing status (e.g. completed, to do)
- Post-processing status
- Editorial notes (e.g. “check completeness of fascicles”, “index missing”)
- Direct link to the digital resource (e.g. Archive.org, DMGH, Google Books)

This organisation became necessary due to the non-uniform structure of the BEF collection, with volumes divided into tomes, fascicles, or thematic sections that do not always correspond to standard bibliographic classifications. As a result, a complex process of bibliographic alignment and source normalisation had to be initiated, aimed at establishing a unified classification system that would allow for the computational processing of the data according to consistent criteria. This work, which is still ongoing, represents the methodological prerequisite for fully integrating the BEF collection into the REVER project, and serves as the foundation for future large-scale extraction and automatic summarisation activities.

4.2.4 Overview of collections excluded from the REVER campaign

Table 6 presents a set of editorial collections of papal registers and regesta which, although analysed, were excluded from the first phase of the automatic processing workflow. The primary reasons for their exclusion include the inconsistent quality of available digital reproductions, the absence of a standardised editorial structure, the partial or fragmentary availability of volumes, and—in some cases—the exclusive presence of regesta without the corresponding full-text documents. This latter condition prevents the alignment between document text and regestum, a requirement essential for automatic summarisation. These limitations have hindered their immediate integration into the processing pipeline. However, their future inclusion remains a possibility, either through targeted pre-processing strategies or within manually assisted workflows involving guided normalisation and comparative analysis.

Collection	Pope	Entity
O.S.B.	<i>Regestum Clementis PP. V. (1305/14)</i> , ed. cura et studio monachorum O.S.B., sed absque indice, Romae 1885 sq. (Table chronologique et Table des Incipit), ed. FAWTIER/LANHERS (BEF), Paris 1950	9 vol 1 suppl
KEHR	<i>Regesta Pontificum Romanorum</i> , Germania Pontificia ed. A. BRACKMANN, Berlin 1911/35	3 vol
	<i>Regesta Pontificum Romanorum</i> , Italia Pontificia ed. P. F. KEHR., Berlin 1906-1935	10 vol
	<i>Regesta Pontificum Romanorum</i> , Gallia Pontificia ed. Vandenhoeck und Ruprecht, 1998-	3 vol
	<i>Regesta Pontificum Romanorum</i> , Dalmatia-Croatia Pontificia ed. W. KÖNIGHAUS usus I. STIPIŠIĆ Schedis	1 vol
PRESUTTI	P. Pressutti, <i>Regesta Honorii III</i> , Roma, 1888/95	2 vol.
EUBEL	<i>Register des Gegenpapstes Nikolaus V (1328/30)</i> ed. EUBEL in Arch. Zschr. 1893.	pp. 123/212
OTTENTHAL	<i>Bullenregister Martin V</i> , ed. Emil von Ottenthal, in <i>Mitteilungen des Instituts für Österreichische Geschichtsforschung</i> , Ergänzungs-Band vol. 1 (1885) p. 401-589	ff., 1894, 661 ff.
JAFFÉ	<i>Regesta Pontificum Romanorum usque ad annum 1198</i> ed. Ph. JAFFÉ, Prima ed Lipsiae 1851, secunda correctata et aucta auspiciis G. WATTENBACH, curaverunt S. LOEWENFELD, F. KALTENBRUNNER et P. EWALD, Lipsiae 1885/88	2 vol

Table 6 – Collections excluded from the REVER dataset.

4.3 External Contribution to the Classification of the BEF Collection

Given the structural complexity of the BEF collection—characterised by volumes subdivided into tomes and fascicles that are not always consistent—a collaboration with external

partners was initiated to support the classification and normalisation of the material. The task involves, for each pope, reconstructing the complete list of existing volumes and fascicles, aligning chronologies, numbering, and bibliographic references, as well as updating the status of work related to scanning, segmentation, and transcription. The need for such intervention stems from the editorial complexity of the collection, which is organised into fascicles, volumes, indices, appendices, etc. This heterogeneity made it necessary to carry out a systematic mapping, capable of providing a unified and functional view for integrating the corpus into the REVER project. Manual information tracking was supported by the development of a control matrix comprising unique identifiers, sequential numbering, and cross-references to source materials. This matrix now functions as a central operational asset for managing the BEF collection, laying the groundwork for its full integration into the automatic processing pipeline.

4.4 Use of Metadata in Dataset Structuring

Beyond their internal tracking function, metadata tables play a central role in the operational structuring of the dataset. The collected data are used to define the selection criteria for volumes to be processed, to support the technical documentation released on platforms such as Zenodo and the ITSERR Marketplace, and to enable cross-quality checks, for instance, to detect missing or duplicate fascicles. Moreover, metadata facilitate the generation of filtered and searchable lists, useful for the development of bilingual annotated datasets or for specific phases of testing and validation. Thanks to their standardised structure, they allow the export of partial views tailored to different purposes: from training and evaluation of models, to teaching activities, and to comparisons between different editions or existing digital versions. In this way, metadata serves not only as documentation tools but also as active components in the design and management of the workflow.

5. User stories and functional specifications

5.1 Functional objectives and user profile

The functionalities defined within the REVER project were shaped by the operational needs expressed by potential users, as identified during the analysis and design phases. These include, in particular, researchers, students, and cultural heritage professionals involved in the processing, analysis, cataloguing and summarisation of medieval papal texts. The main user profile is that of a researcher with a background in history or philology, not necessarily equipped with advanced IT skills, but interested in tools that simplify interaction with complex textual materials. Functional specifications have therefore been modelled on actual needs, related to the consultation, annotation, transformation, and validation of historical documents in a digital environment.

5.2 Summary list of collected user stories

Each user story expresses a concrete need from the perspective of someone using the system, following a typical structure: "As a [type of user], I want [goal] so that [benefit]". This approach allowed the WP7 team to systematically gather user needs that emerged during design, testing, and training activities. The user stories were compiled in a shared spreadsheet and refer to different user profiles—researchers, students, archivists, librarians—covering the full operational cycle of the Reverse Regesta platform: from text upload to segmentation, from transcription to the automatic generation of regesta, through to review and export of the results. A representative selection of these stories is presented in the following section, serving as a basis for interface modelling, feature planning, and assessing the overall design impact of the platform. The main ones from the WP7 team are listed here.

Req. ID	US ID	Initiative	Epic	Title	As A	Description	Acceptance Criteria	Priority
	US-WP7-0002	WP7-RevIt	AI-as-a-Service	Data Collection	Researcher	(E1) I want to visualize the resources used to train the AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ability to visualize and download a list of resources (books) used in the training phase 	MustHave-High
	US-WP7-0003	WP7-RevIt	Cross-Platform	User Profile Management	Researcher	(E2) I want a personal account on REVER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User Access: The user must be able to create a personal account by entering email address and password; Ability to create new collections and libraries of documents in my personal area uploading plain texts on platform; Ability to edit the books (original text and created summaries); Access control: permissions can be set to share with other users the resources or to publish them online; Ability to use the summarization tool online from different devices and with all my metadata always saved in my personal account. 	MustHave-High
	US-WP7-0005	WP7-RevIt	AI-as-a-Service	Data Analysis	Researcher	(E3) I want to automatically summarize a textual document and a collection of books	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ability to modify the collection to adjust and download documents; Ability to work on various projects and collections at the same time; ability to start the automatic summarization on a selected corpus or on the entire collection; 	MustHave-High
	US-WP7-0007	WP7-RevIt	Community and Educational	Collaboration Tools	Researcher	(E4) I want to edit, share and work collaboratively with other (selected) users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Edit the summaries extracted and then save them on my personal account to have a personalized collection of summaries; Create, and manage the annotations (e.g., textual comments, links, H4); External researcher Set sharing options for each of my personal collections (e.g. edit mode for research team or visualisation mode for students); Access Control: Permissions can be set to control who can view, add, or edit annotations. External researcher Visibility Controls: Users can set options to optimize the possibilities of annotations visibility for different purposes (i.e. research, education, etc.) External researcher - people talk search successfully 	MustHave-Medium
	US-WP7-0010	WP7-RevIt	Content Publication	Filtering and Reporting Tools	Researcher	(E5) I want to download the created summaries (i.e. regesta) and my collections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Select from a list of options the various formats (docx, txt, pdf, excel, etc.); Select to download organized or unsorted files; Select to download an entire collection or only a few pages - i.e. download only the summaries or only the extended texts (problem of time and effort); download the entire (summary and extended text); results of summarization; Select from a list of categories which kind of annotation and metadata (e.g. the date and type of document, my annotation on the texts, external links, etc.) 	MustHave-High
	US-WP7-0012	WP7-RevIt	Content Publication	Content Creation Tools	Researcher	(E6) I want to upload the extended texts in various formats (txt, docx, pdf)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Select from a list of options the format (docx, txt, pdf, excel, etc.); Select from a list of categories the type of text (e.g. the date, the typology (letter, decretal, bull, canon, notarial act), and the provenience; 	MustHave-High
	US-WP7-0022	WP7-RevIt	Data Analytics	Analytics and Reporting Dashboard	Researcher	(E7) I want to adopt different summarization options to obtain different summaries starting from the same extended text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ability to select from a list the summarization model depending from the type of extended text I have uploaded; Ability to select from a list which kind of information (tag) extract from the extended text; Ability to create different collections with longer or shorter summaries; 	ShouldHave-Medium
	US-WP7-0024	WP7-RevIt	Cross-Platform	HTB Tagging	Researcher	A number of HTML and annotation tools were used to process the documents used for REVER training. The scriptorium and Iteopias software were customized to work on this typical document.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A report of these resources, a link or an integration with these existing software could be created in the future to facilitate the user by users. 	CouldHave-Low
						(E8) I want to train my AI based on my document collections.		CouldHave-Low
						(E9) I want to create/translate summaries (the regesta) in other languages besides latin.		CouldHave-Low

Table 7 – Selection of user stories collected within WP7.

5.3 Prioritisation and impact on platform design

The user stories collected during the project were classified into four functional categories: MustHave (essential), ShouldHave (important but not critical), CouldHave (optional), and Won'tHave for now (not planned for the current phase). This classification served as a practical tool to guide the initial functional choices for the Reverse Regesta platform. Among the prioritised areas were the design of the user interface for uploading texts and viewing results, export options in ALTO, TXT, and XML formats, multi-user management with collaborative features, and the implementation of tools for control, filtering, and data visualisation via an interactive dashboard.

The integration of these functionalities into the REVER system aligns with the overarching goals of WP7, particularly in terms of technical sustainability, data reuse, and infrastructure

openness. The platform's design was also shaped to ensure maximum adaptability to educational and research contexts across various disciplines, from philology and history to archival science and digital humanities.

6. First experiment in automatic regesta generation on the REVERINO dataset

6.1 Dataset and origin of the text/regesta pairs

The first experiment in automatic regesta generation was carried out using the REVERINO dataset, composed of 4,533 pairs of papal texts and regesta in medieval Latin. As mentioned the text/regestum pairs were constructed from two key critical editions: *Epistolae saeculi XIII e regestis pontificum Romanorum selectae*, published in the *Monumenta Germaniae Historica* (MGH), and *Les Registres de Grégoire IX*, edited by Lucien Auvray and published in the *Bibliothèque des Écoles françaises d'Athènes et de Rome* (BEF).

6.2 Technical pipeline

The automatic regesta generation experiment was based on an experimental pipeline structured into several operational phases. The process began with preliminary manual annotation of the images within the eScriptorium platform, followed by the training of a segmentation model specifically adapted to the structure of the papal texts. Once the images had been segmented, automatic extraction of the linear text was carried out, followed by a post-processing phase aimed at separating the three main components of each document: extended text, regestum, and critical apparatus.

The overall objective was the production of standardised synthetic pairs, to be used as a gold standard for evaluating the performance of language models used in the automatic generation of regesta.

6.3 LLM models tested

During the experiment, three large language models (*Large Language Models, LLM*) were tested: GPT-4o (OpenAI), LLaMA 3.1 70B, and LLaMA 3.1 405B. The aim was to evaluate each model's ability to generate synthetic regesta from papal texts in medieval Latin.

Two distinct strategies were adopted. The first, referred to as *format*, involves the direct generation of the regestum from the original Latin input. The second, termed *backtranslate*, adopts a two-step approach: the Latin text is first automatically translated into English, and the regestum is then generated in Latin based on this intermediate translation. This dual strategy allowed for a comparative assessment of the outputs in terms of both linguistic quality and fidelity to the historical and diplomatic content of the source texts.

6.4 Quantitative results (ROUGE, BLEU)

The performance of the models was evaluated using standard summarisation metrics, specifically ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, ROUGE-L, and BLEU. These metrics respectively measure the lexical overlap between the generated text and the reference text, and the precision in n-grams.

Among the models tested, GPT-4o achieved the best overall performance. For the LLaMA models, the adoption of the backtranslate strategy resulted in a significant improvement in output quality. The results show good lexical coverage but also some difficulties in maintaining the informative structures characteristic of historical regesta, which are often more complex and codified than narrative or argumentative texts.

6.5 Manual qualitative analysis

In parallel with the automatic evaluation, a manual qualitative analysis was conducted on a sample of 20 text/regestum pairs. The aim was to assess the models' ability not only to produce formally correct outputs but also to capture the essential informative elements of historical regesta.

The results showed that GPT-4o correctly identified the recipient in 75% of the cases analysed, while dating was correct in only 3 out of 20 cases. In some examples, the generated regesta proved even richer in information than the originals, thanks to greater fluency and linguistic coherence. However, such expansions resulted in metric penalties due to formal divergences from the reference regesta.

The experiment confirmed the value of the REVERINO dataset as a reliable benchmark for the automatic regesta generation of papal texts in medieval Latin. Although large language models (LLMs) are not yet fully mature for large-scale autonomous use, the results demonstrate the robustness of the developed pipeline and the effectiveness of the annotated pairs for fine-tuning and evaluation activities.

The next steps of the project include expanding the dataset to incorporate new popes and sources, refining the evaluation metrics to obtain more accurate measurements of model performance, and designing dedicated interfaces for the controlled generation of regesta, aimed at professional use and collaborative validation.

The full contribution was presented at the IRCDL 2024 conference and can be accessed at the following link <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3937/short9.pdf>

7. General conclusions

REVER project marks a significant step forward in the digitisation and valorisation of medieval papal sources. By integrating handwritten text recognition (HTR), large language models (LLMs), and a structured analytical methodology, the project has introduced an innovative framework for addressing one of the most complex tasks in diplomatics and historical philology: the automated production of regesta. The outcomes achieved demonstrate not only the technical viability of the proposed workflow, but also its substantial potential in terms of scientific advancement, educational applications, and societal impact.

The development of the REVERINO, REVERINO II, and BEF datasets has resulted in a structured, well-documented corpus designed to serve as a reference resource for the academic community. In parallel, the pilot experiment in automatic regestum generation offers a valuable testbed for the application of generative models in highly specialised historical domains. The interdisciplinary methodology adopted—alongside the involvement of public institutions (universities, research centres, and archives) and active engagement in both scholarly and public dissemination—has enhanced the visibility, replicability, and reusability of the solutions developed within the project.

Looking ahead, WP7 leaves as its legacy not only a methodological and operational infrastructure, but also a set of reusable resources – datasets, tools, training modules – capable of supporting new lines of research, educational paths, and applications in the fields of Digital Humanities and Artificial Intelligence applied to historical studies.

7.1 Achieved results and next steps

At the current stage, WP7 has successfully established and validated a complete technical and methodological framework for the digitisation, processing, and exploitation of medieval papal registers. The workflow has been tested and consolidated through the construction of the REVERINO and REVERINO II datasets, which represent progressively more complex and heterogeneous corpora. These activities have resulted in the development of customised segmentation and transcription models, the definition of consistent metadata structures, and the release of a first high-quality, openly accessible dataset suitable for automatic regesta generation and evaluation of language models.

The work carried out so far demonstrates the robustness and scalability of the adopted pipeline, while also highlighting the challenges posed by increasing documentary variability, particularly in terms of layout heterogeneity, scan quality, and editorial conventions. The REVERINO dataset has served as a controlled benchmark for experimentation, while REVERINO II

has enabled testing the adaptability of the workflow to less normalised sources, requiring more intensive post-processing and quality control.

The next steps of the project will focus primarily on the progressive integration of additional corpora, in particular the remaining volumes of papal registers published by the Bibliothèque des Écoles françaises d'Athènes. This phase will require further refinement of segmentation and transcription models to accommodate a wider range of layouts and typographic patterns, as well as continued bibliographic alignment and metadata normalisation to ensure consistency across collections. Special attention will be devoted to volumes that present mixed structures (tomes, fascicles, indexes, appendices), which will be selectively evaluated to determine their suitability for automatic processing.

In parallel, future work will concentrate on enhancing post-processing strategies for large-scale corpora, combining deterministic heuristics with assisted approaches based on generative models, in order to improve the separation of extended texts, regesta, and critical apparatus. These efforts aim to reduce manual intervention while preserving scholarly control over the integrity of the data.